

ECOLOGICAL CULTURE IN UZBEKISTAN: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. Taking into account the fact that environmental problems are gaining global importance, in recent years, along with important priority tasks, special attention has been paid to environmental protection, ecological culture, ecological education, and ecological awareness. Therefore, the article discusses the issues of forming an ecological culture among the population.

Key words: Ecological culture, ecological knowledge, ecological problem, atmospheric pollution, ecological values.

Introduction. In recent years, environmental problems have become a priority issue in human life around the world. Inequality in nature, global pollution, and climate change - all of this reflects man's attitude towards nature. Uzbekistan is not immune to such problems. Therefore, the formation of an ecological culture in our country and its dissemination to the general public has become an important task.

Taking into account the growing global importance of environmental problems, in recent years, special attention has been paid to environmental protection, ecological culture, ecological education, and ecological awareness, along with important priority tasks.

The relevance of ecological education is determined by the need to protect the nature, ecosystems, and environment of our country from instability and degradation, to increase the ecological culture of the population, and to involve all segments of the population, especially young people, in these serious, vital issues.

The biosphere is changing very rapidly under the influence of human activity. As a result of such an impact of humanity on natural processes, ecological problems began to flare up in the middle of the 20th century. Thus, ecological problems are primarily due to the impact of man on nature.

As a result of the development of civilization and the gradual deepening of humanity's impact on nature, the situation is changing for the worse. Today, even if we talk about primitive pure nature, Because the vast forests on Earth have been cut down, large areas have been cleared for agriculture, fertilizers have been applied, and clean air and nature have been polluted with all kinds of waste and gases. In addition, floods, forest fires, dust storms, and other natural

disasters are occurring more frequently and on a catastrophic scale. All of this is disrupting the natural balance of the environment.

Natural, anthropogenic, or purely anthropogenic phenomena observed around the world are considered universal problems. Such environmental problems include, among others, the phenomena of "Atmospheric Humidification" and "Ozone Layer Depletion", as well as the scarcity of fresh water, the reduction of plant and animal species, and the use of toxic chemical compounds in land cultivation.

Ecological culture is a spiritual, moral, social and practical form of relations between man and nature. That is, it is a person's conscious attitude to nature, the integration of ecological values in his lifestyle, and most importantly, an understanding of personal responsibility for the protection of nature.

Ecological culture includes the following:

1. Ecological knowledge - theoretical and practical information about the state of the environment, natural resources, sources of pollution and their consequences.
2. Ecological feeling - love for nature, the desire to preserve and protect it.
3. Ecological awareness - the ability to understand the impact of a person on nature through his actions.
4. Ecological ethics - the ethics of not harming nature, maintaining a balance between society and nature.
5. Ecological activity - the formation of an ecological lifestyle through practical work (planting trees, sorting waste, saving water, etc.).

Ecological culture is not only information, but also a way of thinking and lifestyle.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS. There are certain obstacles to the formation of an ecological culture in Uzbekistan. Namely:

Firstly, the level of ecological literacy of the population is low. No matter how much information is disseminated, if a person does not have a deep understanding of his impact on nature, he will not understand the consequences of his actions. Many citizens understand the importance of protecting nature, but they do not know how to put it into practice. For example, city dwellers may know what waste separation is, but this concept is not yet widespread in rural areas.

Secondly, there is a lack of information, especially in rural areas. In rural areas, regular access to television, the Internet, and mass media is limited. This prevents people from getting up-to-date information about environmental

threats. For example, in one of the isolated villages of Kashkadarya region, farmers continue to use harmful pesticides on their crops. The reason is that they do not have enough information about modern biological methods. That is, the problem is not knowledge, but access to information.

Third, there is a lack of compliance with environmental standards in manufacturing and agriculture. In many manufacturing enterprises, especially in the small and medium-sized business sector, the implementation of environmental standards is still perceived as an additional cost. For example, it has been revealed that small tanneries in the Syrdarya region discharge their waste directly into the canal, rather than into special treatment facilities. Local residents use this canal water for gardening. This poses a serious threat not only to nature, but also to human health.

Fourth, certain lifestyle habits. People often do not take a critical approach to their daily habits. Leaving water running, throwing garbage outside the trash can, and not sorting paper and plastic are common practices that have serious consequences. For example, in some neighborhoods in the Fergana Valley, it has become a habit to leave the water running for several hours a day in many homes. The reason is that the idea that "water is cheap and plentiful" prevails. But this is a huge loss, especially for a country with a dry climate.

Also, cases of deliberate burning of waste still occur. This leads to air pollution and harm to the respiratory tracts of nearby people, but the population does not fully understand the ecological and medical consequences of this.

Thus, it can be said that the main obstacles to the formation of an ecological culture are not a lack of knowledge, but rather practical approaches, access to information, and difficulties in overcoming old habits. Each example suggests that the problem must be solved not at the individual level, but within the framework of society and infrastructure.

Uzbekistan is a large industrial center and agrarian region, and in the future it is planned to further develop the world-class mechanical engineering, energy, chemical, food industry, and transport complex. The development of such productive forces, in turn, has a certain negative impact on the state of the ecosystem.

According to experts, the most acute ecological and environmental problems in our country today include the following. Firstly, the problems of environmental protection in the regions where large industrial complexes are located, namely Angren, Almalyk, Chirchik, Fergana, Margilan, Navoi and other regions, are particularly acute. The state of the ecosystem in these regions is not

good. Because various gases and wastes emitted by industrial centers lead to pollution of the atmosphere and the environment.

Secondly, environmental problems in the agro-industrial complex.

Thirdly, pollution of natural waters with industrial waste, toxic substances and mineral fertilizers is also among the environmental problems.

Fourth, there are also certain problems with the protection and restoration of flora and fauna, as well as with the expansion of the network of reserves and national parks.

In turn, the main strategic goals of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of nature protection and rational use are the following:

- creation of favorable conditions for the health of the population, preservation of biosphere balance;
- With a view to the effectiveness and sustainability of Uzbekistan's socio-economic development, attention should be paid to maintaining a balance between the processes of production and consumption of renewable natural resources in the use of natural resources, as well as the rational use of waste;
- restoration of the regenerative properties of nature at the regional and national levels;
- preservation of native species of nature and their gene pool, diversity of landscapes;
- improvement of the disastrous ecological situation associated with the Aral Sea problem, etc.

Mammals and birds have decreased in the steppes and forests of our country. The arid areas are teeming with rodents that spread dangerous diseases.

We, humans, are inextricably linked to nature, we cannot live without it. Therefore, we all need to protect and cherish nature, use natural resources wisely, save every drop of water, and always care about the cleanliness of the environment.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS. Today, the development of practical measures to form the ecological culture of the population of our Republic and their implementation are as urgent as water and air. To do this, it is necessary to strengthen

-Environmental education and upbringing. To increase ecological literacy, it is necessary to instill ecological knowledge in the education system. This knowledge should be enriched not only with theoretical, but also with practical training. For example, in the process of teaching the subject "Ecology and Man"

at Tashkent State Pedagogical University, students annually participate in planting forest seedlings in the Buka district. This is not just theoretical knowledge, but also practical experience. Such activities increase the sense of personal responsibility in students. Therefore, it is possible to organize ecological clubs in each school and introduce "ecological day" as a traditional event. This will help children develop a sense of love and responsibility for nature.

-It is necessary to strengthen propaganda work through the media, the influence of television, radio, the Internet and social networks in changing public consciousness is very great. If accurate and effective information is provided through these means, an ecological worldview will be formed in people. For example, the project of the "Green House" TV channel called "Ecological Week" shows daily stories about environmental problems and solutions. This helps the population gain practical knowledge, such as waste sorting and water conservation. It is also effective to strengthen awareness among young people through short, understandable videos on platforms such as TikTok, Instagram, and YouTube.

- It is necessary to cooperate with local communities. Because the participation of local communities, citizens' assemblies and public organizations in the formation of ecological culture is important. If citizens themselves participate in practical work, their responsibility towards nature will increase. For example, in the Navoi region, as part of the "Green Zone" initiative, community beekeeping was organized in cooperation with the local population and schoolchildren. These events not only included planting trees, but also lectures on waste disposal and nature conservation. Thus, a community group of "ecological supervisors" was formed in each neighborhood, and they could organize regular insect and healthy environment campaigns.

-It is necessary to improve the legislative framework and strengthen control. Because, Laws exist, but their implementation, control, and ensuring accountability are the most important issues. If the damage caused to nature remains unaddressed, no measures will yield results. For example, in 2022, a large chemical plant in the Namangan region was fined 1.2 billion soums for exceeding the permissible level of harmful substances into the atmosphere, which caused a lot of public discussion. This situation showed that environmental control can be effective. Therefore, an online reporting platform for environmental violations could be created (for example, through Telegram bots). Also, strengthen the activities of public environmental inspectors.

Each of the above measures is not only theoretically, but also practically justified and can be implemented in our country. The most important thing is that if these things are implemented collectively, an ecological culture can be formed not only in words, but also in our lives to a significant extent.

Ecological culture is an investment in the future. If we take care of nature today, tomorrow we and our children will have the opportunity to live in a healthy environment. The work being done in this area in Uzbekistan is yielding positive results, but this is not enough. If each of us does not make our own personal contribution, it will be difficult to change. Therefore, preserving nature should be considered not only the state, but also every citizen.

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